

Evolving HRM Practices: How Mindfulness and Psychological Well-Being Interventions Address Mental Health Challenges among Nurses in Three Public Hospitals within the Polokwane Local Municipality, South Africa

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In South Africa, nurses carry the responsibility of providing health care services to all communities. It is, therefore, crucial that the healthcare service provides quality service to those who need it. Some of the human resources management factors that may help improve quality healthcare service are to ensure the mindfulness and psychological well-being of nurses. The main purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance among nurses in three public hospitals within the Polokwane Local Municipality. The study will follow a positivism paradigm. A quantitative approach will be followed, using a cross sectional design. The population of the study will comprise of 1287 nurses which include, professional and assistant nurses from all three public hospitals in Polokwane Municipality. A purposive sampling method will be utilised to select the three hospitals. A stratified random sampling method will be used to select participants. A minimum recommended sample size of 297 nurses from the two strata of professional nurses and assistant nurses will be used. This will be determined by the Raosoft sample size calculator. A self-administered questionnaire will be used to solicit data. Descriptive statistics will be used to describe and summarise the demographic information of respondents and the levels of the nurse's mindfulness, psychological well-being, and job performance. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient will be used to specify the relationship between mindfulness, psychological well-being, and job performance. A multiple linear regression analysis will also be used to determine the prediction between the study variables. This analysis will be done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26, with Hayes Process add-in software for mediation.

Keywords: Mindfulness, psychological well-being, job performance, Limpopo, nurses

According to Petersen, Fairall, Bhana, Kathree, Selohilwe, Brooke-Sumner, and Patel (2016), in South Africa, nurses carry the responsibility of providing health care services to all communities through the provision of primary health care up to tertiary levels of health care. It is therefore important to explore different ways which can help nurses to perform to their best of their ability. Hence, this paper aims to investigate whether mindfulness and psychological well-being of nurses can improve their job performance.

Nurse turnover worldwide continues to be one of the major challenges in the health sector which leads to low job performance (Baernholdt & Mark, 2009; Pillay, 2017). Mphephu (2019) support Tshitangano (2013) that factors that contribute to nursing turnover in the province of Limpopo province are factors such as lack of workplace resources and working hours. Hence there are about 300 nurses every month leaving South Africa going to work in other

countries (Tshitangano, 2013). Jeniffer and Sutherland (2016) also found that the U.S. could face a shortage of 800,000 nurses by 2020.

When there is a high turnover in hospitals, fewer nurses will be left to deal with a high workload which might affect their job performance. The optimal workload of one nurse is four patients (Uhunamure, 2018). In rural area, provinces like Limpopo there still have an average of one nurse responsible for 40 patients during a night shift (Uhunamure, 2018). A recent study by Mphephu (2019) in the selected public hospitals in Vhembe District found that 79 percent of the respondents were overloaded by nursing responsibilities.

The increased workload causes nurses to have accidents such as medication errors and procedural errors in the workplace (Tei-Tominaga & Nakanishi, 2018). In Several studies have been conducted on nurse's mindfulness and job performance (Dane, 2013; USA, Lomas, Medina, Ivtzan, Rupperecht, & Eiroa-Orosa, 2017; Europe, Van Gordon, Shonin, Zangeneh, & Griffiths, 2014) Switzerland. However, through the extensive literature search, it is established that only a limited number of studies have been conducted looking at mindfulness and job performance in the South African health sector as well as in the Limpopo Province in particular. Hence, it is imperative for this study to be conducted.

Problem Statement

While Good, Lyddy, Glomb, Bono, Brown, Duffy, and Lazar (2016) pointed out that there has been an increase of growth in the

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literature on mindfulness, however, there is still limited understanding of how mindfulness could be applied in the nursing profession. Ngo, Nguyen, Lee, and Andonopoulos (2020) define mindfulness as a state of actively being able to focus on the immediate moment and practice acceptance in the absence of judgment. The department of health report found that only 15 percent of nursing managers have attended the leadership and management development training (Annual Inspection Report, 2016/17). According to the strategic plan for nursing education, training and practice (2016/17), there has been a steady decline in a formal, dedicated nursing leadership position at national and provincial healthcare services organisations in South Africa with growth in non-nurse practitioners in leadership and management positions.

According to literature, it has been found that due to various unfavourable working conditions such as high workload many nurses are found not to be psychologically well and poor working condition ultimately leads to poor job performance (Lee et al., 2019; Taiwo, 2017). In addition to what has been found in literature, certain work environment factors in South Africa that contribute to low job performance for nurses, include non-conducive physical and psychological surroundings, lack of support from supervisors, and long working hours (Edwards & Titman, 2011). Psychological well-being is defined as the extent to which people experience positive emotions and feelings of happiness (Edwards & Titman, 2011).

The Department of Health in Limpopo Province is experiencing a high turnover of nurses, especially at Polokwane and Mankweng tertiary hospital (Mbombi et al., 2018; Shipalana, 2013). Tshitangano (2013) attributed some factors of nursing turnover in Limpopo province to lack of workplace resources and long working hours. Shipalana (2013) and Ramarope (2015) indicate that health care professionals are leaving their jobs because of factors such as poor management, lack of career development, poor working conditions, workload and poor incentives. All these factors such as high workload, high turnover and lack of training eventually lead to the low job performance of nurses in the Limpopo Province (Makunyane, 2012; Ramakuela, Mundalamo, & Ndou, 2018).

Review of Literature

Mindfulness

Mindfulness is a prominent concept in the health care that has gained attention in research communities in the last two decades (Creswell, 2017; Heidegger, 2016; Mindfulness Research Guide, 2011). However, it has not really been applied in the organisations (Penque, 2019). Brown and Ryan (2012) state that mindfulness is being attentive to and aware of what is taking place in the present moment.

Goodman and Schorling (2012) state that training in mindfulness has been identified as a means of minimising the nurse's burnout, turnover and increasing satisfaction. According to Slagter, Davidson, and Lutz (2011), mindfulness practice has been employed to reduce symptoms of depression, to reduce stress and anxiety.

Programs based on mindfulness models have been adopted in schools, prisons and hospitals to improve job performance of employees (Slagter et al., 2011). One example of this program is mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR). Mindfulness-based interventions implemented in workplaces have been shown to improve employees' mental health (Goodman & Schorling, 2012). These programs promotes stress reduction and increased relaxed

states which will improve nurses decision-making through enhanced situational awareness (Penque, 2019).

Psychological Well-being

According to Ahmadi (2009), the healthcare service relies on the nurses to carry through the day to day duties in ensuring service delivery. The nurses are the ones who have the most direct contact with the patients, therefore it is crucial to ensure that the nurses are at all times psychologically well. According to Klopper, Coetzee, Pretorius, and Bester (2012), given the important role that the nurses play in ensuring the efficiency, effectiveness and sustainability of the health services, it is crucial to understand the importance of psychological well-being among nurses.

Psychological well-being is influenced by personal, interpersonal and environmental factors and changes regularly within the context of life stages and developmental tasks (Tshikovhele, 2015). Furthermore, research has demonstrated that psychological well-being develops through a combination of emotional regulation, personality characteristics, self-identity and life experience (Tshikovhele, 2015).

According to Penque (2019), nurses psychological well-being determines their productivity. It is well known that positive mental strength has an important role in the workplace. Research is constantly establishing a significant correlation between psychological well-being and job performance (Jackson, Schuler, & Jiang, 2014; Usman, 2017; Penque, 2019). According to Jackson, Schuler and Jiang (2014), human resource practices, in particular those which maintain an increase in employee psychological well-being, have gained much attention from scholars and practitioners, especially given their claimed benefits to both staff and the organisation in terms of job performance.

Job Performance

Health care facilities are now becoming increasingly demanding, complex and stressful work environment for the nurses (Sibisi, 2012). Daily, health professionals are exposed to situational factors that can make their work difficult, especially in this situation with the COVID 19 pandemic (Soto-Rubio, Giménez-Espert, & Prado-Gascó, 2020). With this complex and challenging work environment, nurses are still expected to perform to their best of their ability. We have now been in a pandemic situation for over a year, and it does not seem to be coming to an end. This put more pressure on the nurses.

Job performance has become one of the most important concepts in organisations as it assists employers to ensure that employees take ownership and accountability for their tasks. For employees to perform to the best of their ability they should maintain three factors which are skills, effort and the nature of the work condition (Abdulla, 2013). Skills include the knowledge, abilities, and competencies of the employee. The effort is the work that the employee puts to get the job done and the nature of the work condition is the state in which the employee work under which this state influences the employee's productivity. Therefore, the productivity and success of organisations depend on these factors.

According to Zarei Nodee, Sheikhi, HosseinKhani, and Soleimani (2021), nurses have the potential to lead the way in improving health and health care for all, but in order to realise that potential they need to operate in an environment that is safe, empowering, and satisfying. Just as health care workers have

a duty of care to their patients, employers also have the mandatory duty to care for their employees to create a healthy work environment for them (Mohebbi & Eslami, 2020). Mohebbi and Eslami (2020) also adds that the consequence of employers not providing the nurses with the positive environment they need, may lead to an adverse impact towards their job performance.

The Relationship between Mindfulness and Job Performance

Dane and Brummel (2013) and King and Haar (2017) found that in a dynamic work environment, workplace mindfulness is positively related to job performance. Dane and Brummel (2013) and King and Haar (2017) claim that mindfulness contributes to performance by improving flexibility and alertness and guarding against distractions and performance blunder. Taken together, these findings raise the possibility that workplace mindfulness facilitates job performance.

According to Vaculík, Vytásková, Procházka, and Zalis (2016), more mindful nurses seem to be more productive at work. Dane and Brummel (2013) also found that mindfulness is likely to help individuals avoid the errors and mistakes that occur when attention departs from present moment events. It also facilitates self-regulation and enables people to respond to potentially stressful events with greater calmness and less frustration (Dane & Brummel, 2013). Mindfulness enables individuals to effectively cope with a range of experiences which enhances job performance Dane (2011). Dane and Brummel (2013) build on the work of Dane (2011) who maintains that mindfulness may contribute to task performance in a range of ways, it might not be beneficial for all tasks. White (2014) found that nurses who are mindful can work under stressful situation which leads to job performance.

Dane and Brummel (2013) conducted a study on mindfulness and job performance on servers in restaurants in the American Southwest. They found a positive relationship between the two variables. Another study by Van Gordon et al. (2014) also found a positive relationship between mindfulness and job performance on teachers in China. This relationship implies that when employees are mindful, they are most likely to perform better. However, these studies were not conducted on the nurses in Limpopo. The nurses represent the workforce because they are the persons who are connected directly with the patients (Apex-Apeh et al., 2020). Hence, a study of this nature needs to be conducted.

Relationship between Psychological Well-being and Job Performance

Improving the quality of health services, especially hospitals require a strong commitment from each member organization and management of hospitals (Ahmadi, 2009). Factors such as personal problems and a lack of physical or mental readiness to work also contributed to non-productivity (Price, 2000)

Dlamini and Visser (2017) found that psychological distress among nurses is a serious concern and can have several negative effects including poor performance. Employees who are more psychologically well may be seen by their supervisors as more likable and fun to be around. Because people in general, and supervisors in particular, tend to be more tolerant of those they like, they may provide more positive performance evaluations for those subordinates considered to be more psychologically well (Wright & Cropanzano, 2004; Ahmed & Malik, 2019).

A study on psychological well-being and job performance was conducted by Wright and Cropanzano (2004) on lecturer at the University of Colorado Boulder, United States. The results of revealed a positive relationship between the variables. Therefore, employers should take into serious consideration the psychological state of their employees as it predicts job performance. However, the fact that this study was not conducted in the researcher's area of interest, this study is important to be given attention.

Research Purpose

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance among nurses in three public hospitals within the Polokwane Local Municipality. The study is important as it wants to find ways to improve job performance of the nurses as they are backbone of the healthcare services.

Objectives of the Study

- To investigate the influence of mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance.
- To establish the relationship between mindfulness and job performance
- To examine the relationship between psychological well-being and job performance
- To determine which independent variable between mindfulness and psychological well-being contributes the most to job performance

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: There is a positive relationship between mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance
- *H2*: There is a positive relationship between mindfulness and job performance
- *H3*: There is a positive relationship between psychological well-being and job performance
- *H4*: There is a strong positive relationship between mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance

Conceptual Model

A conceptual model is developed based on the previous literature and finding showing the relationship between mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance.

Figure 1.1

Conceptual Framework of Mindfulness and Psychological Well-being on Job Performance

Method

Participants

A stratified sampling procedure was used to determine the study

sample. Using an Online Raosoft sample size calculator, a minimum recommended sample size of 297 respondents was obtained. However, to increase the response rate 500 questionnaires were distributed among the professional nurses and nursing assistants employed in the Polokwane Municipality three public hospitals. (Sample size calculator, 2019).

The hospitals include Polokwane Provincial hospital with professional nurses 356 and 217 nursing assistants, Seshego hospital with professional nurses 98 and 120 nursing assistant and Mankweng hospital campus with professional nurses 327 and 169 nursing assistants (Limpopo department of health, 2018/2019).

Research Design

The study was quantitative in nature using a using a cross sectional design. The design will enable the researcher to obtain the same data from a large group of the population at hand in a standardised way. The information collected from the sample will also be generalised to the targeted population (Pinsonneault & Kraemer, 2014).

Measures

Data were collected using a self administered questionnaire comprised of 3 scales namely a self-designed demographic scale, the mindfulness scale, psychological well-being scale and job performance scale.

Mindfulness was assessed using the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS) (Brown & Ryan, 2003). The scale consists of 15-items which will be scored on a five-point Likert scale with anchors rating from (1) almost always to (5) never. Examples of items used in this questionnaire include; "I could be experiencing some emotion and not be conscious of it until sometime later" and "I break or spill things because of carelessness, not paying attention, or thinking of something else". A previous study which was conducted in public hospital in Malaysia with 136 medical students found a reliability coefficient of 0.95 for this questionnaire (Lan, Rahman, Subramaniat, & Kar, 2014). Furthermore, another study was conducted in the tertiary hospital in Chengdu, China among 168 nurses. The reliability coefficient of MAAS was 0.89, which is considered as good (Xie, Zeng, Lv, Li, Xiao, & Hu, 2020).

The psychological well-being will be measured using the psychological well-being questionnaire (PWB) (Ryff, 1995). The instrument consists of 6 dimensions namely, autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. The questionnaire consists of 18-items. Each item will be scored on a five-point Likert scale with anchors ranging from (1) *strongly agree* to (5) *strongly disagree*. Examples of items used in this questionnaire include; "In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live" and "I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons" and "most people see me as loving and affectionate". In the study by Lee, Tzeng, and Chiang (2019) 296 participants who were registered clinical nurses from medical center in Taipei City, Taiwan participated in this study. The study found good Cronbach's alpha coefficient of all 6 dimensions namely; autonomy 0.65; environmental mastery 0.70; personal growth 0.69; positive relations with others 0.77; purpose in life 0.78, and self-acceptance at 0.70. The overall reliability coefficient of PWB was 0.95 which is considered as good.

Job performance was measured using a job performance questionnaire (Goodman & Svyantek, 1999). The questionnaire

consists of 25-items covering three dimensions: altruism, conscientiousness and task performance. Each item was scored on a five-point Likert scale with anchors ranging from (1) *strongly disagree* to (5) *strongly agree*. Examples of items used in this questionnaire include: "Help other employees with their work when they have been absent" and "Achieve the objectives of the job". In a study by Yusoff, Khan, and Azan (2013) among the university teachers in Pakistan found an acceptable Cronbach's alpha coefficient of all dimensions namely; altruism 0.80, conscientiousness 0.89, and task performance at 0.90 (Pallant, 2020). According to Yusoff, Khan, and Azan (2013), a good Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.83 was found for the overall questionnaire (Pallant, 2020).

Data Analysis

Data analysis is defined as a process of cleaning, transforming, and modelling data to discover useful information for business decision-making (Munch, 2017). Therefore, the data collected in this study were analysed through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics was used to summarise and describe the levels of the nurse's mindfulness and job performance as well as in checking the study sample profile. The analysis includes frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation

In addition, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was used to specify the relationship between mindfulness and job performance.

Results

A total of 300 respondents participated in this study. Descriptive statistical analysis was employed to obtain the frequency distribution of demographic variables such as gender, age, qualification, length of work, rank, and job status of the respondents. Results in Table 1 show that the majority, 189(63%) were females, whereas there were 111 males (37%). The majority of the respondents were between 31-35 years 94 (31.1%). The lowest number of respondents were respondents between 20-25 years 5 (1.7%). Moreover, the majority of the respondents 165 (55%) had a Diploma as their highest qualification. Furthermore, 85 (28.3%) respondents had been in the nursing profession from 6 to 10 years, followed by those who had served in the nursing profession for less than 5 years (55) representing 18.3% of the respondents. Table 1 show that most 236(78,7%) participants in the sample were registered nurses, followed by 55(18,3%) who were nursing assistants. Enrolled nurses who participated in this study were 4(1.3%). Results further show that only 3(1%) Licensed professional nurses took part in the study, while the smallest number of respondents 2(0.7%) were Advanced practice. The majority of the participants 249(83%) were permanently employed, whereas 51(17%) were on contract. This indicates that a larger number of the participants were the permanent nursing staff.

Table 2 summarises Cronbach's alpha coefficients of the overall questionnaires. From the mindfulness questionnaire, a fair Cronbach's alpha of .630 was found. The psychological well-being questionnaire obtained a very good Cronbach's Alpha of .856. Furthermore, Cronbach's alpha of .935 was found for the job performance questionnaire which reflects an excellent co-efficient. Furthermore, the reliability coefficient attained by all constructs is satisfactory as they are above .60 thus showing the consistency and stability of the questionnaires (Hair, Money, Samouel, & Babin, 2003).

Table 1*Demographic Information (N = 300)*

Variables	Category	Frequency	%
Gender	Female	189	63
	Male	111	37
Age (years)	20-25	5	1.7
	26-30	60	20
	31-35	94	31.3
	36-40	74	24.3
	41+	68	22.7
Highest qualification	Certificate	51	17
	Diploma	165	55
	Degree	73	24.3
	Post-graduate	10	3.3
	Any other qualification	1	0.3
Work experience	0-5	55	18.3
	6-10	85	28.3
	11-15	76	25.3
	16+	84	28
Rank	Nursing assistant	55	18.3
	Licensed professional	3	1
	Registered nurse	236	78.7
	Advanced Practice	2	0.7
Job status	Enrolled nurse	4	1.3
	Permanent	249	83
	Contract	51	17

Table 2*Cronbach's Alphas of the Study for the Overall Scale*

Construct	No of items	Cronbach's alpha score	Level of reliability
MASS	15	.630	Fair
PWB	18	.856	Good
JP	24	.935	Very good

Note. MASS= Mindfulness; PWB= Psychological well-being; JP= Job performance

Descriptive Statistics (Measure of Central Tendency, Dispersion, & Normality)

Table 3 shows the descriptive statistics on mindfulness, psychological well-being, and job performance. It measures the central tendency of the constructs by displaying the mean and standard deviation. It also illustrates the normality of the data set analysed using skewness and kurtosis. The mean scores of mindfulness, psychological well-being and job performance were ($M = 4$; $SD = 5.64$), ($M = 4$; $SD = 9.61$) and ($M = 4$; $SD = 15.57$) respectively. This implies that most respondents were in agreement with the statements.

Table 3*Descriptive Statistics Showing Measures of Central Tendency, Dispersion, and Normality of Data*

Constructs	M	SD	Skewness	SE	Kurtosis	SE
MASS	4	5.64	-1.32	.141	3.20	.281
PWB	4	9.61	-1.59	.141	2.30	.281
JP	4	15.67	-2.03	.141	4.03	.281

Note. MASS= Mindfulness; PWB= Psychological well-being; JB= Job performance; M= Mean; SD= Standard deviation; SE= standard Error

Hypotheses Testing: Correlations Results

The Pearson product moment correlation was used to investigate the relationship between mindfulness, psychological well-being and job performance amongst the nurses. The results in table 3 shows that there is a significant relationship between mindfulness and job performance among nursing staff in three public hospitals in Polokwane Municipality ($r = .393^{**}$; $p = .000$), which confirms hypothesis two. Therefore, it can be concluded that as mindfulness improves, job performance among nursing staff in three public hospitals in Polokwane Municipality also improves. The results also show that there is a relationship between psychological well-being and job performance ($r = .825^{**}$; $p = .000$). This shows that for nursing staff in three public hospitals in Polokwane Municipality to improve their job performance, their psychological well-being must also improve. This finding also concurs with hypothesis three.

Table 3*Pearson Correlation Analysis Results among the Variables*

Variables		MASS	PWB	JP
MASS	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig.(2-tailed)			
PWB	Pearson Correlation	.443**	1	
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000		
JP	Pearson Correlation	.393**	.825**	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000	.000	

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Regression Analysis

Regression was employed to investigate whether there is an influence of mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance. The results in Table 4 shows that there is a positive influence on mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance, $\beta = 1.09$, $+ (298) = 1.09$, $p = .000$, $(\beta = 1.321$, $+ (297) = 22.18$, $p = .000$). This means that when nurses are both mindfulness and psychologically well, they will perform better. Jnaneswar and Sulphrey (2021) conducted a study which confirms the results found here.

Regression was also employed to test which independent variable between mindfulness and psychological well-being most contribute to job performance. From the results in table four, psychological well-being has the highest standardised beta coefficient ($\beta = 1.321$, $+ (297) = 22.18$, $p = .000$) contributing to job performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that psychological well-being contributes more to job performance than mindfulness. This finding is supported by Kundi, Aboramadan, Elhamalawi, and Shahid (2020) who revealed a connection between psychological well-being and job performance.

Table 4*Regression Analysis*

Model	β	t	df	p
Constant	-5.706	-1.018	297	.000
Mindful	.093	.920	297	.000
PWB	1.321	22.197	297	.000

Note. MASS = Mindfulness; PWB = Psychological well-being; β = Beta; t = t-value; df = degrees of freedom; p = level of significance

Discussion

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

In the current study, females were the majority participants of the study. These findings agree with Tshitangano (2013) study which revealed that 70% of the nurses in Limpopo Province hospitals are females. The results further revealed that the age group that participated the most in the study was between 31 to 35 years. This means that most of the nursing staff in three public hospitals in the Polokwane Municipality are in their mid-thirties, which is the young adulthood age. The results further showed that most participants hold a diploma qualification. Similarly, Mbombi, Mothiba, Malema and Malatji (2018) conducted a study among nurses in a tertiary hospital in Limpopo province. The results showed that the registered nurses were the majority participants of the study. Furthermore, most participants had 6 to 10 years of working experience in the healthcare service. These results are in line with Mphephu (2019) findings which revealed that a large percentage of nurses in the healthcare sector have 5 to 10 years of experience.

The results also showed that the majority of respondents were permanent employees. This might be influenced by the shortage of nursing staff in the healthcare sector. The nursing profession increases by 10 percent a year, whereas South Africa's population rises by 14 percent, resulting in a progressive scarcity of properly qualified nursing professionals across the country (Uhunamure, 2018).

Discussion of the Questionnaires Reliability

A rule of thumb for labelling Cronbach's alpha coefficient by Hair et al. (2003) which suggests that reliability levels ranging from between .60 and over .90 are reliable was followed in the current study. Therefore, this study revealed that all three questionnaires obtained acceptable Cronbach's alpha coefficients. The highest reliabilities amongst the questionnaires included psychological well-being ($\alpha = .856$), followed by job performance ($\alpha = .935$). Mindfulness questionnaire obtained the lowest alpha coefficient ($\alpha = .630$).

Discussion of Descriptive Statistics

The finding of the study shows the descriptive statistics of mindfulness, psychological well-being, and job performance dimensions through mean scores and standard deviations. Mindfulness found a mean score of ($M = 4$; $SD = 5.64$). The findings showed that most nursing staff in three public hospitals in the Polokwane Municipality were not mindful of their job. The findings further showed a mean score of ($M = 4$; $SD = 9.61$) for psychological well-being. This implies that most of the nursing staff also disagreed with the statement that they are psychologically well. This may be caused by a low percentage of the nursing staff not attending the wellness programs provided by the management. However, they agreed to the statement that they are performing with a mean score of ($M = 4$; $SD = 15.57$). Therefore, one can argue that the nursing staff still perform as even though they are not mindful and psychologically well.

Discussion of Correlation Analysis

The study employed Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients to determine the relationship between mindfulness, psychological well-being and job performance. Pearson correlation

analysis indicated a significant relationship between mindfulness and job performance which confirms hypothesis one. This indicates that when the mindfulness of the nursing staff improves, the more they will perform better at their job. These employees will minimise accidents in the workplace such as giving the wrong prescription to the patients.

A significant positive relationship between mindfulness and psychological well-being was also found. This indicates that mindfulness positively impacts the nurse's psychological health. One would, therefore, argue that there is a relationship between mindfulness and psychological well-being being as is supported by the literature.

The third hypothesis states that there is a positive and significant relationship between psychological well-being and job performance. The current study is in agreement with Dlamini and Visser (2017) on nurses in the Mpumalanga Province of South Africa which revealed that nurses who experience psychological well-being are more likely to avoid making mistakes and accidents which will enhance job performance.

Regression Discussion

Regression was employed to investigate whether there is an influence of mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance. The results in table 4 shows that there is a positive influence on mindfulness and psychological well-being on job performance. This means that when nurses are both mindfulness and psychologically well, they will perform better. Jnaneswar and Sulphrey (2021) conducted a study which confirms the results found here.

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Study Limitations of the Study

This section highlights the limitations of this study. It should be made aware that the current study was conducted in only one Municipality in the Limpopo Province of the Republic of South Africa. Therefore, the results of the study can only be generalised by looking at the Polokwane Municipality.

Furthermore, only three hospitals were also sampled in this study. The findings of this study are, therefore, only representative of a small percentage of selected hospitals in Polokwane Municipality which are Polokwane Provincial hospital, Seshego hospital, and Mankweng hospital campus.

Some respondents were not interested in partaking the research. For example, some of the employees complained that they were occupied due to the pandemic. Other wards did not have enough nursing staff to oversee all the responsibilities. This resulted in a slow response of participants. Hence the collection of data was done in the early morning as it is not busy at that time.

Furthermore, a quantitative research methodology was used because of the nature of the study aims; nonetheless, quantitative research designs have their own set of limitations. In this

study, for example, respondents were not given the opportunity to clarify their responses because structured questionnaires with closed-ended questions were used. As a result, the breadth of the responses is restricted.

Recommendations

The findings in this study showed a positive relationship between mindfulness and job performance. In addition, psychological well-being proved to mediate the relationship between mindfulness and job performance. Therefore, future research should investigate other variables that can enhance the job performance of the nursing staff.

Furthermore, a mixed-methods research design will be highly useful for future research in this field of study, as it will aid in collecting, thoroughly, the experiences of respondents in providing more details about their mindfulness and psychological well-being. The use of questionnaires and in-depth interviews with respondents enables one to acquire more detailed information.

To make the conclusions of the study more appropriate to the entire population of Limpopo Province's hospitals, future researchers sample different hospitals in different Municipalities around the Limpopo Province. This will result in a much broader sample that is more representative of the entire study population.

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